

2nd Evaluation Exercise on Micro Frontends

Provide your personal information and answer the questions on the following pages about the Mercado Aberto application.

What is your full name?

In this exercise, you will need to access two documents:

- Description of the proposed architecture to implement the application using Micro Frontends
- Website with the anti-patterns catalog for Micro Frontends

Access the Nab-bank architecture description.

I was able to access the architecture description

Access the Micro Frontends anti-patterns catalog.

I was able to access the catalog

Architectural Inspection

Assume you are a Junior Developer who is about to start working at *Mercado Aberto*. You have just learned more about the system's architecture and were asked to analyze the MFE architecture:

Would you model the *Mercado Aberto* website using Micro Frontends differently? Would you keep the same MFEs, create new ones, or modify the existing ones? Also consider the screens and fragments.

Did you identify any anti-patterns in the architecture? If so, which ones?

Evolution and Bug Fixes

Answer how you would solve the task below considering you are a developer working at *Mercado Aberto*. Feel free to propose new MFEs, shared libraries, screens and/or fragments, as well as modify existing ones.

Note: consider the architecture described in the PDF document, excluding any changes you may have proposed during the architectural inspection.

Suppose the fragment that displays products the user may be interested in has been updated and now requires a new mandatory parameter — the cart items — to avoid showing products already in the cart. The `mfe-store` is deployed (sent to production), and the cart screen starts showing an error because `mfe-purchase` has not been updated to pass the new parameter.

Fragment that displays products the user may be interested in, from `mfe-store`

What would you do to ensure that the fragment change does not cause an error on the cart screen, allowing the screen's code to be updated later in a gradual and safe manner?

Did you use any anti-pattern to answer this question? If so, mention its name and explain how it helped.

Evolution and Bug Fixes

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Initially, `mfe-store` was designed to support only physical products, such as electronics, clothing, and everyday items. Now, Mercado Aberto wants to add a new

type of product: services (such as consulting, private lessons, and technical support). The `mfe-store` code was built specifically for physical products, including business rules involving shipping calculation, inventory, and handling — none of which apply to services. This makes the new implementation more difficult.

What would you have done during the development of physical product sales to make `mfe-store` more generic and facilitate the implementation of new product types?

Did you use any anti-pattern to answer this question? If so, mention its name and explain how it helped.

Evolution and Bug Fixes

Answer how you would solve the task below considering you are a developer working at Mercado Aberto. Feel free to propose new MFEs, shared libraries, screens and/or fragments, as well as modify existing ones.

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Mercado Pago has realized that it's important for the site to allow users to maintain one or more lists of favorite products. A user can have multiple lists, and each list can be named individually. This feature includes the following visual components:

Screen that displays all favorite items and the user's product lists:

Screen that displays the products belonging to a specific list:

Button to add a product to a list, which opens a modal allowing the user to choose an existing list or create a new one.

Modal to create a new list or add to an existing one

What architectural changes are necessary for the development of the components above?

Did you use any anti-pattern to answer this question? If so, mention its name and explain how it helped.

Evolution and Bug Fixes

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Suppose the cart screen is showing an error that is not related to any component implemented directly on the page itself, suggesting that the issue may come from one of the screen's fragments. What would you do to ensure that an error in a fragment does not make the entire screen unavailable?

What would you do to prevent an error in a fragment from causing a failure across the whole screen?

Did you use any anti-pattern to answer this question? If so, mention its name and explain how it helped.

Evolution and Bug Fixes

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Note: consider the architecture described in the PDF document, excluding any changes you may have proposed during the architectural inspection.

Suppose you are working on the creation of a new MFE. You need to create a new application-type component using single-spa and import all shared libraries, follow common code standards and structure, and register the new MFE in the root-config. You lost a lot of time setting up the new MFE before even starting to develop the actual features. How could you speed up the creation of a new MFE next time?

Did you use any anti-pattern to answer this question? If so, mention its name and explain how it helped.

Evolution and Bug Fixes

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Mercado Aberto is launching Meli+ (meliplus), a loyalty program that offers free shipping on all purchases, cashback, exclusive installment options, and free access to Disney+. This feature includes the following visual components:

Meli+ offer screen: displays the benefits and the available subscription plans.

Terms and conditions screen for the subscription

Offer component with details to be displayed on the home page.

Simple offer component to be displayed in the user's account menu.

Nabson
 Meu perfil >

 Assine com 50% OFF

- Compras
- Histórico
- Perguntas
- Opiniões
- Listas de presentes NOVO

- Empréstimos
- Seguros NOVO
- Assinaturas
- Mercado Play GRÁTIS
- Faturamento

- Vender

- Sair

Offer component for the header.

PREÇO ESPECIAL Assine Total com 50% off por 2 meses

Enviar para Nabson Avenida Cosme Ferr...
 [Categorias](#)
[Ofertas](#)
[Cupons](#)
[Supermercado](#)
[Moda](#)
GRÁTIS
[Mercado Play](#)
[Vender](#)
[Contato](#)
NP Nabson
[Compras](#)
[Favoritos](#)

Modal to choose plan:

Escolha seu plano do Meli+

×

meli+ ESSENCIAL

R\$ 9.90/mês

- + Frete grátis em milhões de produtos a partir de ~~R\$ 79~~ R\$ 29
- + Até 5,6% de cashback nas suas compras no Mercado Livre
- + 0,6% de cashback com seu Cartão de Crédito Mercado Pago
- + Até 3 parcelas extras sem juros nas compras do Mercado Livre
- + Seu dinheiro rende 105% do CDI no Mercado Pago

BLACK FRIDAY

meli+ TOTAL

R\$ 27,99 **50% OFF**

R\$ 13.99/mês por 2 meses

- + Inclui todos os benefícios do Meli+ Essencial
- + Disney+ Padrão com anúncios
- + Deezer Premium por 12 meses
- + 50% OFF na Max e 30% OFF no Paramount+

Continuar Cancelar

Assinatura com renovação mensal e automática. Você pode cancelá-la quando quiser. Ao assinar, você aceita os [Termos e condições do Meli+](#), [Mercado Pago](#), [Ripio](#), [Meli Dólar](#) e declara que não é uma [pessoa dos EUA](#) nem está localizada nesse país.

What architectural changes are necessary for the development of the components above?

Did you use any anti-pattern to answer this question? If so, mention its name and explain how it helped.

Evolution and Bug Fixes

Answer how you would solve the task below considering you are a developer working at Mercado Aberto. Feel free to propose new MFEs, shared libraries, screens and/or fragments, as well as modify existing ones.

Note: consider the architecture described in the PDF document, excluding any changes you may have proposed during the architectural inspection.

Consider the following communication flow between `mfe-purchase`, `mfe-store`, and `mfe-users`:

When a purchase is successfully completed, `mfe-purchase` calls a function received from `mfe-store` as a parameter, in order to update the user's list where the purchased product was included (if it was in any list).

`mfe-purchase` also calls a function received from `mfe-users` as a parameter to update the user's point balance according to the purchase value.

Updating the user's total points causes `mfe-users` to call a function from `mfe-store` that informs the new points total so that new personalized offers can be calculated for the user.

Currently, there is a challenge in updating this flow because a single change may impact communication across all fragments.

How would you increase the independence between the MFEs while maintaining communication among them?

Did you use any anti-pattern to answer this question? If so, mention its name and explain how it helped.

Evolution and Bug Fixes

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Note: consider the architecture described in the PDF document, excluding any changes you may have proposed during the architectural inspection.

Suppose that every time you make a change to `mfe-security`, it is necessary to run manual tests to ensure that the application still works correctly. Note that these tests could be implemented as unit or integration tests. What would you do to ensure quality without the need to manually run the tests?

Did you use any anti-pattern to answer this question? If so, mention its name and explain how it helped.

Finalization

To finish, please answer the question below (it will not impact your grade, so feel free to answer honestly).

Rate your perceived knowledge of Micro Frontends on a scale from 0 to 5 (real number):

BEFORE LEAVING THE LAB, please fill out the feedback form about the anti-patterns catalog.

I have already responded or WILL respond to the feedback form NOW.